

ISUAAAT15-031

MULTIROW PERFORMANCE AND AEROELASTIC ANALYSES OF A COMPRESSOR SUBJECTED TO DISTURBANCES FROM PRESSURE GAIN COMBUSTION

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ABSTRACT

Aiming at radical increase of gas turbine thermal efficiency, novel pressure gain combustion (PGC) processes are being investigated. These inherently unsteady techniques include pulse/rotating detonation, shockless explosion and wave rotor combustion. They all introduce periodic disturbances on the flow dynamics, which strongly challenge performance and aeroelastic design.

The current work appraises to which degree this additional unsteadiness affects an industrial high-pressure compressor (HPC). Single and multirow unsteady computational fluid dynamics and aeroelastic analyses characterize how the induced disturbances travel through the system, driving a departure from the steady state design. Assessments with one to four rows (two stages) delineate how farther upstream the disturbance dynamics must be considered by the performance and aeroelastic designers. To that end, unsteady damping as well as maximum stresses are evaluated.

The nonlinear harmonic balance method is employed to determine the aerodynamic work and corresponding damping. Modal forcing from unsteady time-resolved runs is then projected into the blade surface. The structural response is obtained through harmonic response analyses, in a decoupled fluid-structure interaction (FSI) fashion.

INTRODUCTION

In order to reduce specific fuel consumption, thereby environmental impact and costs, breakthroughs in gas turbine technology are currently sought. These engines encompass aeronautical propulsion, stationary power generation (in simple or combined cycles) as well as other marine and industrial applications, and account for an enormous share of world energy consumption. The vast

demand for such machines motivates the development of novel technological concepts, since current configurations steadily reach a saturated efficiency plateau. Among several of these radical innovations, pressure gain combustion has received considerable attention recently. Thermodynamic improvement with respect to constant pressure combustion has been demonstrated, for example, by [1–3].

The accomplishment of this combustion pressure rise should be achievable by diverse means, such as: pulse detonation combustion [4], rotating detonation combustion [5, 6], shockless explosion combustion [7] or wave rotors [8]. All the aforementioned processes have in common the introduction of unsteadiness into the system (in the stationary and/or rotating frames of reference). These disturbances are detrimental both upstream and downstream the combustor chamber, directly modifying the compressor and turbine boundary conditions, respectively. Because the aerodynamic design is typically accomplished with steady state procedures, more insight is needed to evaluate how the newly introduced disturbances shall affect the engine's performance and structural behavior [9–11].

The current work investigates, with computational fluid dynamics (CFD) and computational solid mechanics (CSM) techniques, how an industrial HPC reacts to such upstream-traveling unsteadiness, veering away from its design point. In a previous work [12], single-stage assessments provided a prior insight into the frequency and amplitude ranges that more strongly influence the unsteady operation. The present manuscript extends the previous analyses to a multirow setup, characterizing the unsteady performance and under which conditions and to which degree the blade structure is additionally loaded.

NUMERICAL APPROACH

The present study analyzes both performance and aeroelastic parameters of the E3E high-pressure compressor, provided by an industrial partner [13, 14], depicted in Fig. 1. It consists of a modern and highly efficient core arrangement for medium takeoff thrust.

FIGURE 1: Rotor of simulated HPC [14].

The general methodology used in this work is depicted in Fig. 2, following the same guidelines as in previous work [12]. Therefore, only the main numerical aspects will be described again here, whereas the reader can find more detailed information (such as grid and time independence studies) in the referred manuscript.

FIGURE 2: Performance and aeroelastic methodology. The disturbance implementation and its aftermath are displayed in green.

As sketched in Fig. 2, a decouple FSI approach is employed as follows. 3D unsteady viscid CFD simulations yield performance parameters (such as isentropic efficiency, total pressure loss and compression ratio), forcing harmonics on the blade surface, as well as the unsteady damping (showing to what degree the disturbances are attenuated or amplified). The forcing

harmonics are obtained by a Fourier decomposition of the pressure signal on the blade surface, after it has reached unsteady convergence.

Afterwards, rotor 6 blisk is selected for the structural assessments. A prestressed modal analysis provides the mode shapes, of which the ones with the lowest frequencies (more energetic) are selected to be used with the energy method [15]. Nonlinear harmonic balance [16] is used to determine the aerodynamic work and therefore the aerodynamic damping. The entire interblade phase angle range is analyzed.

Finally, the modal forcing from the time-resolved CFD runs and the global damping are used in a mode-superposition harmonic response analysis, in order to obtain displacements and stress levels. The presence of extra blade rows downstream the structurally analyzed domain is also discussed and quantified.

The software Ansys CFX and Mechanical [17] are employed as solvers. For the CFD runs, Menter's SST turbulence model [18] is used, with fully turbulent flow assumed. Low-Reynolds calculations are performed (dimensionless wall distance $y^+ \approx 1$ for all solid boundaries). Tip gaps and fillets are accordingly modeled. Total pressure and temperature, as well as flow direction, are implemented as inlet boundary conditions, while static pressure is imposed at the outlet. Radial profiles validated by the manufacturer are utilized. The CFD hexaedra structured grids were generated with AutoGrid5 [19]. The CSM high-order tetrahedra meshes were generated with Ansys Mechanical. More detailed information, such as grid independence studies and mesh topologies, can be found in [12].

The operation with the unsteady perturbations is contrasted with the undisturbed, baseline conditions. The disturbances are implemented as harmonic fluctuations of the outlet (compressor downstream) static pressure $p(\mathbf{x})$, as in Eq. (1). The amplitude and frequency of the disturbance are given respectively by A_d and f_d .

$$p(\mathbf{x}, t) = p(\mathbf{x}) [1 + A_d \cdot \sin(2\pi f_d t)] \quad (1)$$

In this paper, three configurations are simulated: rotor 6 only (1 row, termed R6); stage 6 (2 rows, termed R6-S6) and stages 6 and 7 (4 rows, termed R6-S6-R7-S7). They are shown in Tab. 1. The pitch ratio right downstream of rotor 6 (i.e., between R6-S6) is always kept unitary, so to proper model the upstream-propagating disturbances without phasing error related to rotor-stator interfacing methods. Regarding the two-stage configuration (R6-S6-R7-S7), profile scaling [20] is implemented between rows S6-R7 and R7-S7, to save computational resources. Methods such as time inclining [21] or shifting [22] have not been employed on these last interfaces so not to affect the traveling disturbance frequency, being of high relevance here.

The current work aims at gaining a broad

TABLE 1: Single and multirow CFD domain setups.

Configuration	Rows	Passages	Millions of cells
R6	1	1	0.8
R6-S6	2	7	4.8
R6-S6-R7-S7	4	9	6.2

understanding of the disturbance endurance of a modern engine, both in single- and multiple-row compositions. Along the entire work, particular focus is dedicated to rotor 6, which, due to its blisk design, is expected to be aeroelastically more affected in comparison to downstream non-blisk rows. However, performance and forcing characteristics will also be presented for rows other than rotor 6.

Unsteady damping formulation

Single-domain unsteady damping

An important question to be answer during the design of a turbomachinery component which might be subject to axial traveling disturbances is how far these waves traverse. For that matter, the unsteady damping ϵ is defined in Eqs. (2).

$$\Delta\phi = \frac{\phi_{max} - \phi_{min}}{\phi_{mean}} \quad (2a)$$

$$\epsilon_{2,1} = \frac{\Delta\phi_2 - \Delta\phi_1}{\Delta\phi_2} \quad (2b)$$

$\Delta\phi$ stands for the periodic variation of some (properly space-averaged) quantity in time, divided by its mean. ϕ may represent any state variable which is expected to unsteadily fluctuate in the flow field. Along this work, (total and static) pressure and temperature values are investigated, with appropriate area or mass flow average on axial surfaces adjacent to the rows. The streamwise position of each station is set right before/aft each row (circa 10% of the chord).

Since in this work the disturbances propagate from combustor to compressor, station 1 is here always located upstream of station 2. Stations can divide any general domain, such as single/multiple rows, stages, cavities and so on. The unsteady damping computation should always be carried out after adequate unsteady periodic convergence, and for a few periods (the longest between disturbance and blade passing periods).

The unsteady damping concept is illustrated in Fig. 3, where a propagating wave from station 2 to 1 has its amplitude changed. Figure 3(a) depicts a case where the amplitude of the wave is reduced along its path, therefore

yielding $\epsilon_{2,1} > 0$; on the other hand, Fig. 3(b) shows a wave whose amplitude is increased, producing $\epsilon_{2,1} < 0$. These conclusions are also evident from Eq. (2b). In both cases, the influence of the mean value has been removed, so to ease the visualization.

(a) Attenuation behavior ($\epsilon_{2,1} = 0.5$)

(b) Amplification behavior ($\epsilon_{2,1} = -1.0$)

FIGURE 3: Exemplification of the unsteady damping ϵ concept, for a generic variable ϕ . The wave travels from stations 2 to 1.

Cumulative unsteady damping

Since the unsteady damping is always computed between any two stations, it might be interesting to assess how it behaves cumulatively for n stations. The following notation with left superscript will be used: between stations 2 and 1, define $\epsilon_{2,1} \equiv {}^1\epsilon$. Similarly, between stations $n+1$ and n , define $\epsilon_{n+1,n} \equiv {}^n\epsilon$. In general, the left superscript on ϵ is in the range $i_1, \dots, i_k \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, where $k \leq n$ (the positive integer k is simply a summation index). The closed formula for the unsteady damping $\epsilon_{n+1,1}$ (between stations $n+1$ and 1) is derived on Appendix A, and is given by Eqs. (3).

$$\epsilon_{n+1,1} = \sum_{k=1}^n \sum_{\substack{i_1, \dots, i_k \in \{1, \dots, n\} \\ i_1 < \dots < i_k}} (-1)^{k+1} \prod_{j=1}^k i_j \epsilon \quad (3a)$$

$$= 1 - \prod_{k=1}^n (1 - k\epsilon) \quad (3b)$$

Equations (3) consist of a sum of unsteady damping

products including all the stations between ${}^1\epsilon$ and ${}^n\epsilon$. Note that the strict inequalities in the second sum ($i_1 < \dots < i_k$) in Eq. (3a) imply that the products of ${}^{i_k}\epsilon$ do not have repeated indexes i_k .

For the special case where ${}^1\epsilon = {}^2\epsilon = \dots = {}^n\epsilon \equiv \hat{\epsilon}$ (homogeneous unsteady damping on all rows/stages), Eqs. (3) assume a simpler binomial form, given by Eqs. (4) (note that the right superscript indicates as usual an exponent, not a domain).

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_{n+1,1} &= \sum_{k=1}^n (-1)^{k+1} \binom{n}{k} \hat{\epsilon}^k \\ &= 1 - (1 - \hat{\epsilon})^n \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Table 2 exemplifies the computation of the cumulative unsteady damping for both the general case (Eqs. (3)) and the homogeneous case (Eqs. (4)), for $n = 1, 2$ and 3. It is seen that the cumulative unsteady damping is a polynomial of order n equal to the number of staggered domains. Additionally, the terms with odd powers of $\hat{\epsilon}$ always contribute positively to the final outcome, whereas the terms with even powers negatively.

To further analyze the effect of multiple rows/stages on the unsteady damping, Fig. 4 depicts the cumulative unsteady damping as a function of the single domain homogeneous value $\hat{\epsilon}$, with stations varying from 2 to 11 ($n = 1, \dots, 10$ domains). This situation could represent a multistage compressor whose single-domain (for example, a stage) unsteady dampings do not change significantly among each other. From Eqs. (4), one can estimate, for example, that if $\hat{\epsilon} = 0.75$ for one row, 3 rows are already enough to produce a cumulative unsteady damping of $\epsilon_{4,1} = 0.98$, practically imperceptible by upstream domains. On the other hand, if $\hat{\epsilon} = -0.26$, a slightly negative value, 3 rows manage to amplify twofold the wave amplitude of the unsteady variable ϕ , that is, cumulative $\epsilon_{4,1} = -1.0$. This high sensitivity to $\hat{\epsilon} < 0$ is due to the negative sign associated with the even powers in Eqs. (4).

The sensitivity of the cumulative unsteady damping $\epsilon_{n+1,1}$ with respect to the number of stations n can be found by investigating its partial derivative, as in Eq. (5). This equation is defined only for $\hat{\epsilon} < 1$, which is always the case from the definition of ϵ .

$$\frac{\partial(\epsilon_{n+1,1})}{\partial n} = (\epsilon_{n+1,1} - 1) \cdot \ln(1 - \hat{\epsilon}) = -(1 - \hat{\epsilon})^n \cdot \ln(1 - \hat{\epsilon}) \quad (5)$$

The corresponding plot for Eq. (5) is depicted in Fig. 5. Focusing on the first quadrant ($\hat{\epsilon} \geq 0$), which is the case of interest for attenuation purposes, it is clear that all values of the derivative are positive. This means that the addition of further rows/stages for a homogeneous $\hat{\epsilon} > 0$ will always increase the cumulative unsteady damping. The curve

FIGURE 4: Cumulative unsteady damping $\epsilon_{n+1,1}$ as a function of the homogeneous single domain $\hat{\epsilon}$ value (Eq. (4)).

quickly flattens, however, with an increase in n . The loci of maxima is also shown in Fig. 5, with coordinates given analytically by

$$\left(\hat{\epsilon}_{max}, \frac{\partial(\epsilon_{n+1,1})_{max}}{\partial n} \right) = \left(1 - \frac{1}{e^n}, \frac{1}{n \cdot e} \right).$$

$\hat{\epsilon}_{max}$ has its upper limit at $n = 1$ (namely 0.6321), for an integer number of domains. In other words, the maximum sensitivity in attenuation gain always decreases with the addition of further domains, approaching zero monotonically as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

UNSTEADY PERFORMANCE RESULTS

In this section, the unsteady CFD results will be presented for the three simulated configurations (as in Tab. 1), R6, R6-S6 and then R6-S6-R7-S7. In all cases, the domain was extended both upstream of the first row and downstream of the last (between one and two chord length in each direction), so to minimize numerical damping effects associated with the imposed boundary

TABLE 2: Exemplification of cumulative unsteady damping $\epsilon_{n+1,1}$ computation. Shown for first $n = 3$ domains.

Number of domains, n	Number of stations, $n + 1$	Cumulative ϵ $\epsilon_{n+1,1}$	General case Eqs. (3)	Homogeneous case Eqs. (4)
1	2	$\epsilon_{2,1}$	${}^1\epsilon$	$\hat{\epsilon}$
2	3	$\epsilon_{3,1}$	${}^1\epsilon + {}^2\epsilon - {}^1\epsilon^2\epsilon$	$2\hat{\epsilon} - \hat{\epsilon}^2$
3	4	$\epsilon_{4,1}$	${}^1\epsilon + {}^2\epsilon + {}^3\epsilon - {}^1\epsilon^2\epsilon - {}^1\epsilon^3\epsilon - {}^2\epsilon^3\epsilon + {}^1\epsilon^2\epsilon^3\epsilon$	$3\hat{\epsilon} - 3\hat{\epsilon}^2 + \hat{\epsilon}^3$

FIGURE 5: Derivative of cumulative unsteady damping $\epsilon_{n+1,1}$ with respect to the number of domains n .

conditions, particularly perceptible in the presence of disturbances. Therefore, direct numerical comparisons between absolute performance parameters (e.g. losses) would be slightly influenced by the axial length of these domain extensions with respect to the row axial size itself. However, since normalized values are presented for confidentiality reasons, the different configurations can be contrasted without trouble.

R6

The assessment of rotor 6 only, isolated from adjacent vanes, simulates how a single blade row behaves in the presence of upstream-traveling disturbances. The runs mimic the periodic choking (possibly leading to stall) noticed by the blades right upstream of a PGC chamber, as described for example in [11, 23, 24].

Figure 6 shows the R6 total pressure loss ω_{R6} (normalized by the unsteady undisturbed case) as a function of several disturbances frequencies and two amplitudes. The disturbance frequency is shown at the bottom as a multiple of the blade passing frequency (BPF) and at the top by the Strouhal number (defined here as $St = (f_d c_r) / v_{axial}$, for a reference rotor chord c_r and an axial inlet velocity v_{axial}).

FIGURE 6: Normalized R6 total pressure loss ω_{R6} , as a function of disturbance frequency f_d and amplitude A_d .

Firstly, lower disturbances frequencies induce higher losses in the system. For $f_d = 0.125$ BPF, an increase in ω_{R6} of almost 40% is observed, for a disturbance amplitude $A_d = 20\%$. For $A_d = 10\%$, the increase in ω_{R6} was approximately 10% or less for all disturbance frequencies. Finally, for frequencies close to or higher than the BPF, no significant increment in ω_{R6} is observed.

This behavior can be explained by the duration of the interaction between the disturbance wave and the flow dynamics at the blade row. Effectively, the disturbance wave alters the mass flow periodically, offsetting the rotor

from its (unperturbed) design condition. When the high-pressure half of the wave approaches the rotor trailing edge, an increase in the incidence angle is observed, leading to a temporary separation on the suction side of the blade (the flow reattaches before the next wave comes). On the other hand, when the low-pressure half of the wave approaches the trailing edge, small negative incidence angles ensue, in a choke-like temporary behavior. Both these departures from the design point explain the observed increase in total pressure loss. However, the necessary time for the blade to reestablish its “design-point flow” is shorter for the higher frequency than the lower frequency disturbances, which explains the results in Fig. 6.

The unsteady damping ϵ_{R6} for rotor 6 is depicted in Fig. 7, for static pressure and temperature. The subscripts denoting the stations have been dropped, considering that for all cases here computed the wave travels upstream, and the station position is clearly stated. Values are shown for disturbance amplitudes of $A_d = 10\%$ and $A_d = 20\%$. Very similar plots are produced for total pressure and total temperature, not shown here for brevity.

FIGURE 7: Rotor 6 unsteady damping ϵ_{R6} , for static pressure and temperature.

For $f_d < 0.5$ BPF, a significant drop in ϵ_{R6} takes place, becoming even negative for $f_d = 0.125$ BPF. This means that the rotor only was not capable of effectively chopping the disturbance wave, which even increased in amplitude for the lowest simulated frequency. To the authors knowledge, this situation has not been yet

reported in the literature for such upstream propagating disturbances. This result advocates the importance of evaluating how farther these waves propagate, and motivates the assessment of multirow setups, as in the following sections.

R6-S6

This setup encompasses a whole HPC stage, traveling the disturbances first through the stator (S6), followed by the rotor (R6). The change in isentropic efficiency as a function of disturbance frequency and amplitude is displayed in Fig. 8. For this setup, a significant drop in efficiency takes place for $f_d = 0.25$ BPF, with $A_d = 20\%$, plunging almost 25%. Although the lowest frequency wave ($f_d = 0.125$ BPF) theoretically offsets the optimal operation point for a longer time, once its pressure peak traverses the stage, there is enough time for the flow to reestablish itself, specially the temporarily separated zones. This is not the case for $f_d = 0.25$ BPF, when, as soon as the flow starts to reattach onto the blade surfaces, the next wave peak arrives, disrupting again the system. This behavior is particularly stronger on the suction side of the blades and vanes. Therefore a larger decrease in efficiency is observed for $f_d = 0.25$ BPF.

FIGURE 8: R6S6 isentropic efficiency η_{R6-S6} variation, function of disturbance frequency f_d and amplitude A_d .

The unsteady damping for this configuration comprises the whole stage (that is, station 2 is located downstream of S6, while station 1 is located upstream of R6), being shown in Fig. 9. A very similar behavior to the R6-only runs is observed, where the $f_d = 0.125$ BPF disturbance yields negative ϵ_{R6-S6} for the static pressure wave propagation with $A_d = 10\%$. For both disturbance amplitudes, the static temperature virtually does not have its amplitude changed, being on the verge of crossing the border from attenuation to amplification.

(a) Disturbance amplitude $A_d = 10\%$

(b) Disturbance amplitude $A_d = 20\%$

FIGURE 9: Stage 6 unsteady damping ϵ_{R6-S6} , for static pressure and temperature.

R6-S6-R7-S7

In order to check how the disturbances propagate in a multistage configuration, four rows were simulated within the same disturbance frequency range as before. With this setup, it is possible to check how the performance parameters and modal forcing change in a stage in the presence of an extra stage downstream. In case, for example, the design of one specific row presents aerodynamic or aeroelastic constraints, the disturbance attenuation/amplification effect of rows downstream might be of high interest.

Figure 10 depicts how the isentropic efficiency varies in the presence of disturbances, with respect to the transient undisturbed case. The scale is kept the same for all figures. Due to the fact that the disturbances initially meet stage 7, a clearly more pronounced drop in efficiency is observed in Fig. 10(b), reaching $\Delta\eta_{R7-S7} = -25.4\%$ for a disturbance frequency of $f_d = 0.125$ BPF and amplitude $A_d = 20\%$. Indeed, for all runs with $A_d = 20\%$, the drop in efficiency surpassed 10%.

The effect of the disturbances on stage 6 efficiency is much weaker, as seen on in Fig. 10(a). The drop is restricted to less than 5% for all cases, except for $f_d = 0.125$ BPF and $A_d = 20\%$. This fact impacts on the combined response of the two-stage setup in Fig. 10(c). Now the total variation lies between the values of stage 6 and 7, being still perceptible for the design point of view, particularly for $A_d = 20\%$.

To illustrate how farther upstream the disturbances travel in this two-stage configuration, Fig. 11 displays the

(a) Stage 6

(b) Stage 7

(c) Stages 6 and 7

FIGURE 10: R6-S6-R7-S7 isentropic efficiency variation as a function of disturbance frequency f_d and amplitude A_d . Values shown for each stage and for the whole domain.

unsteady damping for the whole domain. For $f_d \geq 0.5$ BPF, $\epsilon_{R6-S6-R7-S7} \approx 1$, meaning that the disturbance is almost completely attenuated along the two stages. On the other hand, and similarly to the previous results for other row setups, a clear decrease in unsteady damping is observed for low disturbance frequencies, reaching negative values for $f_d = 0.125$ BPF. To additionally portray this last case,

Fig. 12 shows the static pressure percentage variation in time (analogously to Fig. 3(b)), after convergence is achieved. Here, the variation in pressure increases from station 2 to 1, therefore yielding a negative unsteady damping value.

(a) Disturbance amplitude $A_d = 10\%$

(b) Disturbance amplitude $A_d = 20\%$

FIGURE 11: Stages 6 and 7 unsteady damping $\epsilon_{R6-S6-R7-S7}$, for static pressure and temperature.

FIGURE 12: Static pressure percentage variation on R6-S6-R7-S7 setup, for $f_d = 0.125$ BPF and $A_d = 20\%$. The unsteady damping is $\epsilon_{R6-S6-R7-S7} = -0.322$ (amplification).

The unsteady damping values for the static pressure are also shown in Tab. 3, separately for each stage and for the whole domain. One observes that the cumulative damping relations from Eqs. (3) are readily verifiable. That is, $\epsilon_{R6S6R7S7} = [1 - (1 - \epsilon_{R6S6}) (1 - \epsilon_{R7S7})]$.

TABLE 3: Unsteady damping values for static pressure in the R6-S6-R7-S7 setup, for each stage and accumulated. Results for disturbance amplitude $A_d = 20\%$ and several disturbance frequencies.

Frequency	Stage 6	Stage 7	Stages 6 and 7
f_d (BPF)	ϵ_{R6-S6}	ϵ_{R7-S7}	$\epsilon_{R6-S6-R7-S7}$
0.125	-0.167	-0.133	-0.322
0.250	0.516	0.403	0.711
0.500	0.831	0.881	0.980
0.750	0.784	0.920	0.983
1.000	0.959	0.858	0.994

STRUCTURAL RESULTS

As depicted in Fig. 2, the main goal of the CSM simulations is to perform harmonic response analyses. The displacements and stresses are assessed in this work only for the rotor 6, which, due to its blisk design, lacks friction damping, relying mostly on the aerodynamic damping from the flow field. Hysteretic damping can be safely ignored for the blade material [25, 26].

Based on the energy method, the aerodynamic damping for this blade and the present baseline operating conditions has been obtained in a previous work [12], with the nonlinear harmonic balance method. Figure 13 depicts the normalized damping ratio ξ as a function of the nodal diameter (or alternatively interblade phase angle), for the first three blade-dominated natural modes. The modal forcing comes from the unsteady CFD computations, and, along with the damping ratio, is used in mode-superposition harmonic analyses. In this work, to match the disturbance pattern, the minimum global damping for zero nodal diameter was used. It is indeed close to the minimum damping for the modes here studied, which entails a conservative approach with respect to the structural results.

The maximum von-Mises stresses on the rotor 6 blade are shown in Figs. 14. The normalization is done with respect to the stress value of the run $f_d = 1$ BPF and $A_d = 20\%$ (for each respective row setup).

Firstly, one notices a strong correspondence between increase in pressure loss (Fig. 6) and drop in efficiency (Fig. 8 and Figs. 10) with increase in forcing on blade 6. Particularly, the unsteady damping results (Figs. 7, Figs. 9 and Figs. 11) serve as a good indicator of expected additional structural loading. Secondly, the increase in the maximum stress values is much more pronounced for the lower frequencies, namely $f_d = 0.125$ BPF and 0.25 BPF, with values reaching almost 250 times the corresponding stresses for $f_d = 1$ BPF.

To provide an idea of how the forcing varies along

(a) First three blade-dominated natural modes, with displacement contours.

(b) Damping ratio normalized

FIGURE 13: Damping ratio ξ as a function of nodal diameter, for the first three blade-dominated natural modes (shown with scaled aspect ratio).

the four rows simulated in this setup, Fig. 15 depicts the probability density of the static pressure distribution harmonic corresponding to the $f_d = 0.25$ BPF and $A_d = 20\%$, for the rotor blades and stator vanes. The distribution was obtained from the pressure values (after a Fourier decomposition) taken from each blade/vane surface and plotted together. It is clear that the peak in amplitude of the pressure harmonic decreases from vane S7 monotonically upstream until blade R6 (from right to left in the horizontal coordinate), with different variances. This result matches qualitatively the unsteady damping outcome, which also shows an upstream decrease in wave amplitude for this frequency.

CONCLUSIONS

Unsteady aerodynamics and aeroelasticity numerical analyses were performed for a HPC subjected to pressure gain combustion disturbances. The concept of unsteady damping as a descriptor for axially-traveling wave endurance was presented and analytically explored. Single and multirow calculations showed how much a modern core compressor departs from its optimal design point in the presence of upstream-traveling disturbances. The main takeaways from this work are:

1) From the performance viewpoint, the number of rows (or stages) to be simulated in the presence of disturbances is strongly dependent on the wave amplitude (in this work termed A_d). For “weak enough” waves (here

(a) R6

(b) R6-S6

(c) R6-S6-R7-S7

FIGURE 14: Maximum von-Mises stresses on R6 blade, for different CFD row setups. Horizontal normalization by the amount corresponding to $f_d = 1$ BPF and $A_d = 20\%$.

roughly with $A_d < 10\%$ of outlet pressure), detectable but not serious depreciation in efficiency and stability was encountered. However, for larger amplitudes (such as $A_d = 20\%$), a decrease as high as 25% was observed. In summary, the upstream-traveling pressure waves from PGC might not be a performance show-stopper, as long as the amplitudes are kept within reasonable limits. This may be achieved by a proper unsteady combustion scheduling design, an effective plenum geometry etc.

2) The unsteady damping (defined in Eqs. (2)) was shown to be a good descriptor of an unsteady

FIGURE 15: Probability density of the static pressure harmonic from the R6-S6-R7-S7 setup, with $f_d = 0.25$ BPF and $A_d = 20\%$. Values depicted for all blades/vanes.

turbomachinery flow subjected to waves that travel in the axial direction. It represents quantitatively whether a wave is attenuated or amplified along its path, and to each degree. Although it was used to assess temperature and pressure, any other periodically varying state variable might be investigated. Additionally, the unsteady damping cumulative formulation (Eqs. (3) and Eqs. (4)) sheds light into how much local unsteady damping should be expected from each station of a multirow/stage turbomachinery component to achieve a global attenuation. Its validity was checked in a two-stage disturbed setup.

3) With the aid of the unsteady damping, an outcome has been obtained, not previously reported in the literature for this type of upstream-propagating wave analysis. For all setups simulated (rotor only, one and two stages) subject to a disturbance frequency of $f_d = 0.125$ BPF, an amplification of the pressure wave was observed. That is, a negative unsteady damping value was retrieved, indicating the potential need for modeling several stages, according to the sensibility desired with respect to the disturbances aftermath.

4) The CSM results indicated a meaningful increase in displacements and stresses on the rotor blade analyzed, in the presence of disturbances. This phenomenon is particularly stronger for lower engine order excitations, being almost 250 times more intense for $f_d = 0.125$ BPF and 0.25 BPF compared to the $f_d = 1$ BPF case. All blade row setups showed similar increase trends. Additionally, a clear coherence is found between stress levels and the unsteady damping. This agreement might be particularly interesting in the design phase, where preliminary unsteady CFD calculations can already hint what trends would be expected in the structural analyses, according to how farther and with which intensity the disturbance waves travel.

NOMENCLATURE

A_d	disturbance amplitude
c	reference chord
f_d	disturbance frequency
p	pressure
St	Strouhal number ($St = f_d c_r / v_{axial}$)
v	velocity
\mathbf{x}	spatial coordinates vector
y^+	dimensionless wall distance

Greek

ϵ	unsteady damping
η	isentropic efficiency
ξ	damping ratio
ϕ	generic state variable
ω	total pressure loss

Subscripts

$\epsilon_{2,1}$	streamwise station numbering
${}^1\epsilon$	streamwise domain numbering

Abbreviations

BPF	blade passing frequency
CFD	computational fluid dynamics
CSM	computational solid mechanics
HPC	high-pressure compressor
PGC	pressure gain combustion

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors greatly acknowledge the support from the Berlin International Graduate School in Model and Simulation based Research (BIMoS), as well as Rolls-Royce Deutschland Ltd & Co KG. for providing the test case data. The helpful discussions with Ciro Sobrinho Campolina Martins about the mathematical formulation are also deeply appreciated.

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APPENDIX A

UNSTEADY DAMPING FORMULATION

CUMULATIVE UNSTEADY DAMPING DERIVATION

As discussed in the paper, the unsteady damping ϵ models how an axially traveling wave (with constant frequency) has its amplitude changed along the turbomachinery system. Particularly, whether the wave amplitude is increased (amplification) or decreased (attenuation or damping), as it traverses single or multiple domains. What is here meant by *domain* is a wave-carrying medium between two axial stations. Some domain examples are: a single row (such as a rotor or stator passage), a stage (rotor and stator), a cavity etc.

The definition of the unsteady damping between stations 2 and 1 is repeated in Eqs. (A.1) for convenience. ϕ stands for some (properly space-averaged) state variable in time.

$$\Delta\phi = \frac{\phi_{max} - \phi_{min}}{\phi_{mean}} \quad (\text{A.1a})$$

$${}^1\epsilon \equiv \epsilon_{2,1} = \frac{\Delta\phi_2 - \Delta\phi_1}{\Delta\phi_2} \quad (\text{A.1b})$$

Here, left superscripts refer to the domain, while the right subscripts refer to the station order (domain n is therefore located between stations $n + 1$ and n , for $n \geq 1$). In the current convention, the wave travels from station 2 to station 1. Since the axial positioning of the stations is arbitrary, both upstream and downstream traveling waves may be modeled without restriction. If the wave travels one further station, termed 3, the unsteady damping between stations 3 and 2 is therefore

$${}^2\epsilon \equiv \epsilon_{3,2} = \frac{\Delta\phi_3 - \Delta\phi_2}{\Delta\phi_3} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

whereas the cumulative damping $\epsilon_{3,1}$ between stations 3 and 1 is

$$\epsilon_{3,1} = \frac{\Delta\phi_3 - \Delta\phi_1}{\Delta\phi_3} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

Isolating $\Delta\phi_1$ from Eq. (A.1b) and $\Delta\phi_3$ from Eq. (A.2), and subsequently plugging them into Eq. (A.3), one obtains

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_{3,1} &= 1 - (1 - \epsilon_{2,1})(1 - \epsilon_{3,2}) \\ &= 1 - (1 - {}^1\epsilon)(1 - {}^2\epsilon) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

In a similar fashion, n stations yield a cumulative damping $\epsilon_{n+1,1}$ given by

$$\epsilon_{n+1,1} = \sum_{k=1}^n \sum_{\substack{i_1, \dots, i_k \in \{1, \dots, n\} \\ i_1 < \dots < i_k}} (-1)^{k+1} \prod_{j=1}^k i_j \epsilon \quad (\text{A.5a})$$

$$= 1 - \prod_{k=1}^n (1 - {}^k\epsilon) \quad (\text{A.5b})$$

Here, indexes $i_1, \dots, i_k \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, where $k \leq n$ (the positive integer k is simply a summation index). Equation (A.5a) provides a direct way to compute all terms as a sum of products, while Eq. (A.5b) provides a more intuitive approach to obtain the cumulative damping.

The identity between Eqs. (A.5a) and (A.5b) can be demonstrated by an inductive argument. The case with $n = 1$ is trivially satisfied. Supposing the identity is true for n and expanding Eq. (A.5b) for $n + 1$:

$$\begin{aligned}
 1 - \prod_{k=1}^{n+1} (1 - k\epsilon) &= 1 - (1 - (n+1)\epsilon) \prod_{k=1}^n (1 - k\epsilon) \\
 &= 1 - \prod_{k=1}^n (1 - k\epsilon) + (n+1)\epsilon \prod_{k=1}^n (1 - k\epsilon) \\
 &= \sum_{k=1}^n \sum_{\substack{i_1, \dots, i_k \in \{1, \dots, n\} \\ i_1 < \dots < i_k}} (-1)^{k+1} \prod_{j=1}^k i_j \epsilon + (n+1)\epsilon \prod_{k=1}^n (1 - k\epsilon)
 \end{aligned} \tag{A.6}$$

Applying again the inductive hypothesis, the last term in (A.6) is expanded as

$$\begin{aligned}
 (n+1)\epsilon \prod_{k=1}^n (1 - k\epsilon) &= (n+1)\epsilon \left[1 - \sum_{k=1}^n \sum_{\substack{i_1, \dots, i_k \in \{1, \dots, n\} \\ i_1 < \dots < i_k}} (-1)^{k+1} \prod_{j=1}^k i_j \epsilon \right] \\
 &= (n+1)\epsilon - \sum_{k=1}^n \sum_{\substack{i_1, \dots, i_k \in \{1, \dots, n\} \\ i_1 < \dots < i_k}} (-1)^{k+1} \prod_{j=1}^k i_j \epsilon (n+1)\epsilon \\
 &= (n+1)\epsilon - \sum_{k=1}^n \sum_{\substack{i_1, \dots, i_k \in \{1, \dots, n\} \\ i_{k+1} = n+1 \\ i_1 < \dots < i_k}} (-1)^{k+1} \prod_{j=1}^{k+1} i_j \epsilon \\
 &= (n+1)\epsilon - \sum_{k=2}^{n+1} \sum_{\substack{i_1, \dots, i_{k-1} \in \{1, \dots, n\} \\ i_k = n+1 \\ i_1 < \dots < i_{k-1}}} (-1)^k \prod_{j=1}^k i_j \epsilon \\
 &= (n+1)\epsilon + \sum_{k=2}^{n+1} \sum_{\substack{i_1, \dots, i_{k-1} \in \{1, \dots, n\} \\ i_k = n+1 \\ i_1 < \dots < i_{k-1}}} (-1)^{k+1} \prod_{j=1}^k i_j \epsilon \\
 &= \sum_{k=1}^{n+1} \sum_{\substack{i_1, \dots, i_{k-1} \in \{1, \dots, n\} \\ i_k = n+1 \\ i_1 < \dots < i_{k-1}}} (-1)^{k+1} \prod_{j=1}^k i_j \epsilon
 \end{aligned} \tag{A.7}$$

Substituting this term in expression (A.6), one obtains

$$\begin{aligned}
 1 - \prod_{k=1}^{n+1} (1 - k\epsilon) &= \sum_{k=1}^n \sum_{\substack{i_1, \dots, i_k \in \{1, \dots, n\} \\ i_1 < \dots < i_k}} (-1)^{k+1} \prod_{j=1}^k i_j \epsilon + \sum_{k=1}^{n+1} \sum_{\substack{i_1, \dots, i_{k-1} \in \{1, \dots, n\} \\ i_k = n+1 \\ i_1 < \dots < i_{k-1}}} (-1)^{k+1} \prod_{j=1}^k i_j \epsilon \\
 &= \sum_{k=1}^{n+1} \sum_{\substack{i_1, \dots, i_k \in \{1, \dots, n+1\} \\ i_1 < \dots < i_k}} (-1)^{k+1} \prod_{j=1}^k i_j \epsilon
 \end{aligned} \tag{A.8}$$

completing the proof.

Homogeneous unsteady damping

A more strict assumption would be that the unsteady damping (for some particular disturbance characteristic) does not differ among domains. This homogeneous value is here denoted as $\hat{\epsilon}$. For this special case, ${}^1\epsilon = {}^2\epsilon = \dots = {}^n\epsilon \equiv \hat{\epsilon}$. Now Eqs. (A.5) take a binomial form, as in Eqs. (A.9). This formulation corresponds to a binomial expansion with negative sign for even powers of $\hat{\epsilon}$.

$$\epsilon_{n+1,1} = \sum_{k=1}^n (-1)^{k+1} \binom{n}{k} \hat{\epsilon}^k \quad (\text{A.9a})$$

$$= 1 - (1 - \hat{\epsilon})^n \quad (\text{A.9b})$$

As discussed in the paper, the sensitivity of the cumulative unsteady damping with the number of stations is obtained by the partial derivative of $\epsilon_{n+1,1}$ with respect to n . Although physically the variable n only assumes integer values, the domain of the function $\epsilon_{n+1,1}(\hat{\epsilon}, n)$ is extended onto the \mathbb{R}^2 so to obtain the derivative with respect to n , analytically given by

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial(\epsilon_{n+1,1})}{\partial n} &= (\epsilon_{n+1,1} - 1) \cdot \ln(1 - \hat{\epsilon}) \\ &= - (1 - \hat{\epsilon})^n \cdot \ln(1 - \hat{\epsilon}) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.10})$$

where the requirement $\hat{\epsilon} < 1$ is already satisfied by the very definition of the unsteady damping.

Finally, for $\hat{\epsilon} > 0$, the maximum of the curves described by Eqs. (A.10) should provide the value for which the highest gain in cumulative damping takes place. This point can be found by

$$\frac{\partial^2(\epsilon_{n+1,1})}{\partial n \partial \hat{\epsilon}} = 0 \quad (\text{A.11})$$

and finally solving for $\hat{\epsilon}$, now named $\hat{\epsilon}_{max}$. The coordinates obtained, which constitute the loci of maxima, are given by

$$\left(\hat{\epsilon}_{max}, \frac{\partial(\epsilon_{n+1,1})_{max}}{\partial n} \right) = \left(1 - \frac{1}{e^n}, \frac{1}{n \cdot e} \right) \quad (\text{A.12})$$

Alternating unsteady damping

A slightly less restrictive assumption would be to alternate the unsteady damping every other domain. For example, if the rotor rows are expected to provide more/less damping than the stator rows. Defining the unsteady damping for domains with odd and even indexes respectively as ${}^{ODD}\epsilon$ and ${}^{EVEN}\epsilon$, Eq. (A.5b) becomes

$$\epsilon_{n+1,1} = 1 - \left[(1 - {}^{ODD}\epsilon) (1 - {}^{EVEN}\epsilon) \right]^{\frac{n-1}{2}} (1 - {}^{ODD}\epsilon) \quad \text{for } n \text{ odd} \quad (\text{A.13a})$$

$$\epsilon_{n+1,1} = 1 - \left[(1 - {}^{ODD}\epsilon) (1 - {}^{EVEN}\epsilon) \right]^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \quad \text{for } n \text{ even} \quad (\text{A.13b})$$

The effect of alternating unsteady damping on the cumulative damping can be seen in Fig. A.1, where only 1 to 3 domains are shown for clarity. The ratio between the odd and even unsteady damping values is given by the factor $f = {}^{ODD}\epsilon / {}^{EVEN}\epsilon$. This formulation might be useful when the designer has a better idea of how the disturbances change in amplitude along specific domains.

FIGURE A.1: Cumulative damping $\epsilon_{n+1,1}$ for alternating case. Odd and even domains values are given respectively by $ODD \epsilon$ and $EVEN \epsilon$.